

Design and Parametric Analysis of a Stand-Alone Solar-Hydro Power Plant with Pumped Water Storage Technology

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Abstract

There is a global over reliance on fossil fuel for energy generation which has triggered global alarm on climate change due to greenhouse gases emitted by fossil fuel. These harmful effects of fossil fuel on the environment have tilted global effort towards harnessing renewable energy sources which is obviously the future of energy. In this paper, the design and parametric analysis of a stand-alone solar-hydro power plant using pumped water storage technology is presented. It is aimed at addressing the growing concern of bulk energy generated from renewable energy sources. The paper adopted the University of Uyo main campus as its case study site, performed a load demand profile assessment on a section of the campus, obtained the meteorological data of the site, and designed a 250 kVA solar-hydro power plant with pumped storage technology. The results of the Matrix laboratory (MATLAB) simulation revealed that when the generating head of the upper reservoir was increased from 20 m to 100 m, the required generating flow rate decreased from 1.0994 m³/s to 0.2199 m³/s. It also revealed that, an increase in the pipe diameter from 0.2 m to 1 m, decreased the equivalent head losses from 337.04 m to 0.0878 m.

Keywords: Pumped storage hydropower, bulk energy storage, renewable energy, stand-alone, green battery.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is the world's most populous black nation and it is endowed with abundant natural resources but in the face of these vast natural endowments it has been facing energy crisis that has been hindering its economic advancement for many years (Suleiman, 2010). It is a known fact that energy is one of the basic elements for economic development and it is also the mainstream of all human activities in this 21st century (World Energy Council [WEC], 2016). This highly insufficient and epileptic power situation in Nigeria has led to individuals, corporate and government organizations making substitute provisions for electric power in their establishment by means of installing several generators with a variety of power capacity (Ikponmwosa, Olawale, Adedayo, Dickson & Kenechi, 2014). This energy crisis has affected

businesses, raised cost of production in Nigeria and by extension supported inflation and a decrease in the standard of living of Nigerian Citizens.

The energy mix statistics of Nigeria have shown evidently that more than 90% of electricity produced in the country are generated from fossil fuel even in the presence of abundant renewable energy sources (RES)(Edozien, 2016). A research conducted by World Energy Council (2016) revealed that more than 89% of electricity generated globally are produced from fossil fuel. Following the apparent over reliance on fossil fuel by so many countries, there is an alarm on climate change due to greenhouse gases emitted mainly by fossil fuel. These harmful effects of fossil fuel on the environment have tilted global effort towards harnessing RES.

Future power generation is primarily skewed towards the deployment of RES for energy generation. This is simply because sustainable energy sources have been proven to be environmentally safe, abundant in nature, easily applicable and non-toxic to human (Ajayi, Ohijeagbon, Nwadialo, & Olumide, 2014). The global effort to generate more power from renewable sources of energy and other non-pollutant modules has its own issues to grapple with. However, RES are intermittent in nature.

The main issue with a lot of renewable energy generation technologies is the presence of unequal level of load-following flexibility compared to the fossil fuel based energy generation (Barbour, Wilson, Radcliffe, Ding, & Li, 2016).RES are climate dependent as a result they are inconsistent, mostly unreliable and they cannot inherently stored in their raw form as in the case of fossil fuel-based generation. Based on the forgoing, storage mechanism is always required to store the excess energy generated from RES.

The storage mechanism often used in Nigeria is battery storage. Most designs in the nation including the research conducted by (Babatunde, 2007; Dumkhana & Idoniboyeobu, 2018; Orhorhoro, Orhorhoro & Ikpe, 2016), amongst others used battery as their storage mechanism. The main issue with battery storage mechanism is its relatively short life span which has made it almost impractical for bulk power storage. This is because the cost of replacement of battery which recurs every three to five years is unbearably high. As a result it is uneconomical for bulk energy storage while pumped water storage (PWS) has been noted for its longevity (more than 100 years), as such it is considered viable and attractive for bulk power storage.

This research focused on integrating PWS technologies into a stand-alone solar photovoltaic (PV) system. This work offers the possibility of addressing the challenges of variation in the energy generated by the intermittent RES. Since the sunlight and wind energy are not constant and there is uncertainty about their availability when they

are required, the surplus energy generated by the sun are stored in the form of water using pumped storage system instead allowing it to waste.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS

Some empirical studies conducted in the area of pumped water storage are presented in this section. Notton, Lazarov & Stoyanov (2011) analyzed pumped hydroelectric storage for a wind/PV system for grid integration with a view to solving the major problem associated with large scale use of RES. In the paper, surplus electrical energy generated by the renewable energy systems were transformed in potential energy by pumping water to the elevated reservoir where it was stored and then allowed to flow through hydraulic turbines and generate electricity.

Again, Yohannes (2018), conducted a feasibility study of wind and solar powered pumped hydro energy storage system for isolated grid application in Amhara Region of Ethiopia. The research identified wind, solar and hydro energy source as attractive to Ethiopian as it enjoys good wind speeds, high solar energy potential and large rivers. The report emphasized the suitability of pumped storage hydro (PSH) technology for converting huge quantities of electrical energy to potential energy by pumping water to a higher elevation, where it is stored and then allowed to flow through turbine on demand and its ability to balance the fluctuating load demand from consumers or unplanned outages of other power plants. Also Ekoh, Unsal, & Maheri, (2016) adopted similar approach in their report.

In addition, Ilupeju & Inambao (2017) presented a report on power generation in a small hydropower system using pumped storage technology. The researchers designed a 300 kW hybrid power plant (conventional Hydropower and PSH) to generate electricity from a running river. When the energy demand is less (off peak hours), the surplus power generated is used to pump water from the reservoir at ground level to the elevated reservoir. At peak hours when the energy demand is higher, the water stored in the upper reservoir is released to generate power to supplement the conventional hydropower plant. Modeling of the design was carried out with MATLAB Simulink to ease simulations and all essential parameters were mathematically modeled.

Furthermore, Ohiero, Odey & Ukang (2018) proposed a system that consist of an underground water storage tank, solar PV system, battery bank, inverter, a water pump, overhead water tank, a water turbine and a generator. The proposed design is intended to work in such a way that the surplus power generated by the PV module is deployed to pump water from the lower reservoir to the elevated tank. Once the elevated reservoir is filled, water is conserved in the elevated reservoir while the PV

module, inverter and battery supply the required power to the load and when the load demand increases, water is released from the overhead tank through the turbine to generate electricity.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Description of Study Site and Solar Radiation Data of the Site

University of Uyo (UNIUYO) main campus was selected as the case study site. The site is located along Nwaniba road in Uyo, the capital of Akwa-Ibom State in the south-south region of Nigeria. The UNIUYO main campus has a coordinate of latitude 5.0308 North and longitude 7.9198 East and covers an area of about 14.43 km². The average temperatures of the institution range from 20.12 °C to 32.42 °C as revealed by data obtained from National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) website. The site coordinates were used to retrieve the meteorological data in CSV format from the NASA website.

3.2 Technical Analysis of an Integrated Solar Hydro Power Plant

In this research, a 250 kVA stand-alone integrated solar hydro power scheme using pumped water storage technology was designed, as depicted in the design layout in Figure 1. The design consists of seven steps as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Layout of the integrated solar hydro power plant

Figure 2: Flow Chart for the Design of an Integrated Solar Hydro Power Plant

3.3 Estimation of the Load Demand and Selection of Adequate Size of the Generator

In order to obtain an appropriate load demand profile of the selected section of the University of Uyo, visits were made to the case study site and a comprehensive record of the equipment/appliances used in the affected offices were taken. Table 1 shows the load demand profile of the affected section of the case study site. The power ratings used for the various equipment are based on different type of manufacturers as such the minimum and maximum values were retrieved and the average computed and used. The load demand of the site is approximately 167 kW and expressed in terms of average voltage and current with power factor of 0.8 gives 208 kVA. The generator size was selected with due consideration of system losses and safety margins of the system components. Hence, the total estimated load was multiplied by a factor of 1.2 in order to compensate for future increase in the load demand, the system losses and safety margins. Eventually, a 250 kVA hydro-turbine generator was considered suitable for the purpose.

The hydro part of the system has an effective head of 30 m and turbine efficiency of 0.93 (based on the data from the hydro turbine used for the design). The volumetric flow rate of the system is calculated as follows:

$$Q_g = \frac{P_g}{\rho g \eta_t H_g} \quad (1)$$

Where: Q_g is the rated flow rate (generation) in m^3/s , P_g is the rated generated power in kW, ρ is the density of water at 25°C in $\text{kg}/\text{m}^3 = 997 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$, g is the gravitational constant in $\text{m}/\text{s}^2 = 9.81 \text{ m}/\text{s}^2$, η_t is the turbine efficiency = 0.93 and H_g is the rated generating head in $\text{m} = 30 \text{ m}$.

Rated power in kVA (P_{kva}) = 250 kVA, then Rated Power in kW (P_g) is give as

$$P_g = P_{kva} \times \text{Power factor} \quad (2)$$

Where power factor = 0.8

Now, $P_g = 250 \times 0.8 = 200 \text{ kW}$

Substituting the data into Equation 1 gives:

$$Q_g = \frac{200000}{997 \times 9.81 \times 0.93 \times 30} = 0.73 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

It is normally recommended to keep the flow losses at less than 10% of the head (Ilupeju, 2015). Andaroodi (2006) recommended a flow velocity in the range of 1.5 m/s to 2.5 m/s in order to achieve a realistic pipe size that will maintain the pipe losses within 10% of the effective head. Using a flow velocity of 2 m/s, the pipe diameter can be estimated as follows:

$$A = \frac{\pi d_g^2}{4} \quad (3)$$

$$d_g = \sqrt{\frac{4A}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

$$A = \frac{Q_g}{V} \quad (5)$$

$$d_g = \sqrt{\frac{4Q_g}{\pi V}} \quad (6)$$

Where A is the area of pipe in m^2 , d_g is the generating pipe diameter in m , V is the velocity of flow in m/s , Q_g is the generating flow rate in m^3/s , π is the constant = 3.142

Therefore,

$$d_g = \sqrt{\frac{4 \times 0.73}{\pi \times 2}} = 0.68 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, the approximate value of the generating pipe diameter size is 0.7 m

Table 1: Load demand profile of the selected section of the case study site

S/N	Appliances/Loads	minimum watt (W)	Maximum watt (W)	Avg-watt (W)	Nos	Total Wattage (kW)	Use hours per day	Total Wattage-hours (kWh/day)
1	Air conditioner	1119	2984	2051.5	31	63.5965	10	635.965
2	Ceiling fan	150	150	150	30	4.5	10	45
3	Photo copy machine	200	500	350	25	8.75	8	70
4	Printer	250	500	375	35	13.125	8	105
5	Laptop	60	120	90	60	5.4	10	54
6	Desktop computer	150	500	325	50	16.25	8	130
7	Television	100	400	250	5	1.25	8	10
8	Refrigerators	250	500	375	30	11.25	24	270
9	Water dispenser	150	300	225	30	6.75	8	54
10	Phone/tablet charger	5	15	10	90	0.9	8	7.2
11	Electric Kettle	1500	3000	2250	10	22.5	8	180
12	Indoor light fitting	20	100	60	60	3.6	8	28.8
13	Security light fitting	250	400	325	30	9.75	12	117
14	Total	4204	9469	6836.5	486	167.6215	130	1706.965

3.4 Determination of the Size of the Reservoirs for the PSH System

The reservoir is a major component of the stand-alone pumped water storage hydropower plant. The system autonomy for this design is 3 days. The rated generating flow rate per seconds is $0.73 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, to determine the generating flow rate per day, the generating flow rate per seconds was multiplied by a conversion constant of 86400 ($60 \times 60 \times 24$). The rated generating flow per day is $63,072 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ and it was multiplied by 3 days of system autonomy to obtain the minimum reservoir capacity. The minimum reservoir capacity was multiplied by a sizing factor (SF) of 1.1 to compensate for losses in the pipe network. Therefore, $208,137.6 \text{ m}^3$ ($95 \times 95 \times 24\text{m}$) reservoir capacity is required for continuous power generation for the three days of system autonomy.

3.5 Determination of the Number and the Capacity of the pump

The pump required for this project was designed with the consideration of the project parameters like pumping head, pipe losses, volume of water required in the upper reservoir, daily sun hour of the site and the pump efficiency. The power (P_p) required to pump water to the elevated reservoir was calculated as follows:

$$P_p = \frac{\rho g Q_p [H_p + H_{p1}]}{\eta_p} \quad (7)$$

Where: P_p is the rated pumping power in kW, ρ is the density of water at 25 °C in kg/m³, Q_p is the rated pumping flow rate in m³/s, g is the gravitational constant in m/s², H_p is the rated pumping head in m, H_{p1} is the major head losses in m and η_p is the pump efficiency.

With reference to the average volume (69,379.2 m³) of water required to generate electricity for the one day and the solar radiation data retrieved from the NASA website, which shows that the site enjoy up to 11 hours of sunlight daily. This implies that the water will be pumped for 11 hours, then:

$$Q_p = \frac{69379.2}{60 \times 60 \times 11} = 1.75 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

Steel pipe with 0.6 m diameter was selected for this design to account for relatively lower head loss. Darcy-Weisbach head loss equation shown in Equation 8 was employed in the calculation of the major head losses H_{p1} .

$$H_{p1} = \frac{fLV_p^2}{2gd_p} \quad (8)$$

Where; f is the Darcy-Weisbach friction factor (unitless), L is the rated pumping head (m), V_p is the velocity of fluid in the pumping pipe (m/s), d_p is the diameter of pipe (m) and g is the gravitational constant (m/s²)

$$V_p = \frac{Q_p}{A_p} \quad (9)$$

where: A_p is the area of the pumping pipe (m²).

$$A_p = \frac{\pi d_p^2}{4} = \frac{\pi \times 0.6^2}{4} = 0.3 \text{ m}^2$$

$$V_p = \frac{Q_p}{A_p} = \frac{1.75}{0.3} = 5.83 \text{ m/s}$$

The Darcy-Weisbach friction factor was computed with Swamee-Jain friction factor equation given as:

$$f = 0.25 \left\{ \log \left(\frac{\epsilon/d_p}{3.7} + \frac{5.74}{Re^{0.9}} \right) \right\}^{-2} \quad (10)$$

Where: ϵ is the roughness of pipe, Re is the Reynold number and d_p is the diameter of pipe (m),

$$Re = \frac{V_p d_p}{\nu} \quad (11)$$

Where ν is the kinematic viscosity of water at 25 °C = 8.917×10^{-7}

$$Re = \frac{2.22 \times 0.6}{8.917 \times 10^{-7}} = 0.15 \times 10^7 = 1.5 \times 10^6$$

ϵ is the steel pipe roughness, 45×10^{-6} m

$$f = 0.25 \left\{ \log \left(\frac{45 \times 10^{-6}/0.6}{3.7} + \frac{5.74}{(1.5 \times 10^6)^{0.9}} \right) \right\}^{-2} = 0.013$$

The value of f , L , V_p , d_p , and g were substituted into equation 8 to give

$$H_{p1} = \frac{0.013 \times 30 \times 5.83^2}{2 \times 9.81 \times 0.6} = 1.13 \text{ m}$$

The pumping flow rate is relatively high; hence pumping the required volume of water with a single unrealistically high pump capacity is grossly uneconomical. The U.S. Department of Energy (2006) revealed that connecting pumps in parallel can be a cost-saving solution to the use of single pump with very large capacity and it also reduces system down time in the case of a fault on one pump. Based on the foregoing, 10 identical pumps with an average flow rate of $0.175 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was used in the design of the PSH system since parallel pump network increases flow rate by adding the individual pumps flow rate.

$$Q_{p10} = \frac{1.17}{10} = 0.175 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

The rated pumping power of each pump can be computed with Equation 7

$$P_p = \frac{997 \times 9.81 \times 0.175 [30 + 1.13]}{0.90} = 59.2 \text{ kW.}$$

3.6 Determination of the Number of PV Module Required for the Water Pumps

The key parameter required for the determination of the number of PV module has been computed in the previous section of this research. The output power of the PV module can be computed with Equation 12

$$P_m = \eta(T_{op}, S_r) S_r A_{tm} \quad (12)$$

Where: P_m is the power output of the PV module, $\eta(T_{op}, S_r)$ is the overall efficiency of the PV module (it incorporate the effect of temperature on the module performance), S_r is the solar radiation, A_{tm} is the total area of PV module per pump.

$$\text{But } \eta(T_{op}, S_r) = \eta(25^\circ C, S_r)[1 + K(T_{op} - 25^\circ C)] \quad (13)$$

Where: $\eta(25^\circ C, S_r)$ is the efficiency module under standard test condition (STC), K is the temperature coefficient of the cell, T_{op} is the operating temperature of the PV module.

Data available on PV module data sheet and NASA website show that $T_{op} = 32^\circ C$, $K = -0.41\%/^\circ C$ and $\eta(25^\circ C, S_r) = 18.3\%$. These values were substituted into Equation 13 to compute the overall efficiency of the module. Hence,

$$\eta(T_{op}, S_r) = 18.3\% [1 - 0.0041(32^\circ C - 25^\circ C)] = 17.8\%$$

From Equation 12, A_{tm} is given as:

$$A_{tm} = \frac{P_m}{\eta(T_{op}, S_r) S_r} \quad (14)$$

The value of P_m was obtained by multiplying P_p with the proposed daily pumping hours (11 Hours). Therefore, $P_m = 59.2 \times 11 = 651.2 \text{ kWh}$, $S_r = 10.58 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$ (obtained from NASA website), $\eta(T_{op}, S_r) = 17.8\%$. These values were substituted into Equation 14 to obtain the total area of PV module per pump.

$$A_{tm} = \frac{651.2}{0.178 \times 10.58} = 345.8 \text{ m}^2$$

To obtain the number of modules, equation 15 was utilized.

$$N_m = \frac{P_m}{\eta(T_{op}, S_r) S_r A_m} \quad (15)$$

Where N_m is the number of module per pump, A_m is the area of each module. ($A_m = 1.77 \text{ m}^2$)

Total number of PV module per pump $N_m = \frac{651.2}{0.178 \times 10.58 \times 1.77} = 195.4$ modules, approximately 196 modules. Hence, the PV array consist of 7 x 28 strings, that is 7 modules were connected in series and 28 parallel strings.

The 10 identical pumps required for the entire PSH would utilize a total of 3458 m^2 of land space and 1960 PV modules.

4. RESULTS

The design of the standalone solar-hydro power plant with pumped water storage technology was carried out in section 3 of this paper. Based on the design parameters, simulation were carried out with MATLAB.

For a given output power of the hydro system (in this case, 250 kVA) the volumetric flow rate decrease with increase in the rated generating head of the upper reservoir. Figure 3 describes the variation of the rated generating head with the volumetric flow rate of the system. The turbine output power was kept constant at 250 kVA while head was varied from 20 m to 100 m and the corresponding values of the flow rated also varied from 1.0994 m to 0.21988 m. The result shows that, the higher the generation head, the lower the flow rate required. Conversely, the lower the head, the higher the flow rate required for same output power.

Figure 4 describes the behaviour of the integrated system when the power is held constant and head varied from 20 m to 100 m. As shown evidently in Figure 4, for a given output power, the reservoir size decreases as the head is increased. In other words, for a fixed rated power, the reservoir size required at higher head is smaller than the reservoir size at lower head.

Figure 3: Variation of the rated generating head with the volumetric flow rate

Figure 4: Relationship between rated generating head and reservoir capacity

For a given volume of water or reservoir capacity, the energy generated increase with a corresponding increase in head as shown in Figure 5. This is because, the flow rate required to generate a certain quantity of power decrease as the generating head increase. Since the flow rate decrease with head, it takes a longer time to drain a fixed reservoir capacity and by implication more energy. Therefore, more energy is generated at higher head. While the graph in Figure 5 shows the variation of head and energy generated, the cursor point indicates rated generating head used in the design and the energy that the given reservoir size can produce.

The relation between the diameter and the head losses for a given flow rate is shown in Figure 6. Head losses occur due to change in the head pressure between the inlet and the outlet of the flow line. It can be observed from the Figure 6 that the head losses decreases sharply with increase in pipe diameter.

Figure 5: Variation of generating head with energy generated at 208,137.6 m³

Figure 6: Variation of pipe diameter with respect to head loss

5. CONCLUSION

This research focused on integrating solar and hydro power plant using pumped water storage technology for a stand-alone system instead of the usual battery storage. It requires the use of two reservoirs (lower and upper reservoir). PV modules were used to pump water from the lower reservoir to the elevated reservoir. The energy stored in the form of water in the elevated reservoir is allowed to flow through a turbine to the

lower reservoir hence electricity is generated. The result obtained from the analysis asserts that for a given output power of the hydropower system, the volumetric flow rate decrease with increase in the rated generating head of the upper reservoir. The research affirmed in one of the results obtained that for a fixed rated power, the reservoir size required at higher head is smaller than the reservoir size required at lower head and that for a given reservoir capacity, the relationship between energy generated and rated generating head is linear

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